

RAILWAYS OF UZBEKISTAN ARE DEVELOPING ON THE BASIS OF TIME REQUIREMENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11098428>

Annotation: This article mainly analyzes the progress made in improving the performance of railways during independence in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Statistical data is also provided in the chronological sequence.

Keywords: International routes, railway traffic, locomotives, freight transportation, farm cargo transportation, passenger safety, electrification, Black railway, trays, relief, metal well, precautions and details.

Аннотация: В данной статье в основном анализируются реформы, проведенные в Республике Узбекистан в годы независимости по улучшению работы железных дорог. Статистические данные также представлены в хронологическом порядке.

Ключевые слова: Международные маршруты, железнодорожное сообщение, локомотивы, грузоперевозки, перевозки сельскохозяйственных грузов, безопасность пассажиров, электрификация, Кнудовая железная дорога, локомотивы, рельеф, металлическое литье, запасные части и детали.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada asosan O'zbekiston Respublikasida mustaqillik yillarida temir yo'llar faoliyatini yaxshilash borasida olib borilgan islohotlar haqida tahlillar boradi. Shuningdek, xronologik ketma-ketligida statistik ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Xalqaro yo'nalishlar, temir yo'l harakat, lokomotivlar, yuk tashish, xo'jalik yuklarini tashish, yo'lovchilar xavfsizligi, elektrlashtirish, Qamchiq temir yo'l, teplovozlar, relyefli, metall quyuv, ehtiyot qism va detallar.

Railway transport is now operating for the economy of our country. In turn, our state and government are also heavily connected to this network focuses. Major changes are being made in the field of railways in the country. Today, the transportation of the railway system is carried out at the level of time requirements. The number of passengers has been increasing year after year. The system provides conditions for passengers. The stations have waiting seats for passengers, maternal and children's rooms, playrooms for children, dining rooms. A hotel complex has also been built at the Central Station in Tashkent, with 9 luxurious and 5 standard rooms. In the carriages, television devices are installed, and passengers can leave watching national music and artistic films

until they reach their destination. In addition, passengers are being given hot meals in wagon-restaurants and coupe-buffets. The cost of the ticket on trains traveling internationally includes three meals a day.

In the next decade, the composition of railway traffic in our country was greatly updated, complete with 38 modern electric locomotives, 10 trays carrying passenger cars, and 150 modernized locomotives. Annual passenger traffic reached 20 million people by 2015 and freight traffic reached 82 million tons. Currently, 60% of the country's household cargo and 75% of passengers are transported by rail.

In recent years, uzbek railways JSC has been working on large-scale projects. A number of laws on railways have been drafted. To assist individuals desiring to benefit the worldwide work of Jehovah's Witnesses through some form of charitable giving, a brochure entitled Charitable Planning to Benefit Kingdom Service Worldwide has been prepared. To assist individuals desiring to benefit the worldwide work of Jehovah's Witnesses through some form of charitable giving, a brochure entitled Charitable Planning to Benefit Kingdom Service Worldwide has been prepared. As a result of the law, the most advanced security systems have been created at the stations of Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Andijan, Urgench, and Qarshi. At the entrance to the station, an interscope, metallodetector, gazoanalyzer and detectors for checking hand luggage and luggage are installed at the entrance to the station. Separate entry-exit routes will be opened to create additional support for passengers.

Under the auspices of the JSC "O'ztemiryo'lyo", 28 stations were constructed, 17 stations were built during the years of independence, and 8 were reconstructed. For example, stations such as Ab'i-gail, Boysun, Darband, Gulf, Uchkuduk, and Na'a-man. These stations are not only the achievement of the railway system, but also appeal to foreign sycamores by adding blindness to the blindness of our country's cities.

On June 18, 2013, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted resolution PQ-1985 on measures to organize the construction of the Electrified Angren-Pop railway line, Under this decision, the construction of a new railway line and its unique part, a 19.2-mile [19.2 km] tunnel, was commissioned by railwaymen, located 2,000 feet [2,000 m] above sea level, and this construction was commissioned by railways in 2016 it was put into use in August, prematurely. During the construction, more than four thousand people were employed, and one thousand five hundred permanent jobs were created. The black railway tunnel ranks eighth in terms of difficulty in construction in the

world, and ranks first in length in the world and among CIS countries. In addition, a new Railway Tashkent-Boysun-Kumkogon consisting of 223 km, 6 stations, 37 bridges, khayraton–Mozori Sharif of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan was commissioned to be used. The tashkent-Khockent, Tashkent-Angren, Tashkent-Samarkand routes have also been electrified, and today a total of 1,700 km of railways have been fully electrified. Railways were also electrified on the Maroqand-Qarshi route and 325 km on the Qarshi-Thermal route.

The unitary enterprise "Uztemiryo'lmashta'mir" is the first industrial enterprise in the railway system, with a history of 116 years. The unit company meets the needs of the railroad system and the precautions of the high road structure, determination of residual resources of the rolling content, diagnostic work. The company successfully implements orders not only of JSC "Uzbekiston temir yullari" but also of the Navoi mining and metallurgical combinat and "Uzbek coal", large industrial enterprises of the republic. During the years that followed, the plant is rapidly mastering new production methods with the most modern technological processes. There is also a great deal of emphasis on the modernization of trays. For example, 2T210M-Russian trays produced modern "UZTE16M" russian trays of 2, 3 and 4 sectors by introducing 1A9DG Russian engines with a capacity of 3,000 horses and changes related to the parts of the trays, and today are being used with high flour in densely located areas of our country's complex reefs and industrial enterprises.

The subsidiary of the Mining and Mechanical Plant also does not contribute appropriately to improving the country's economy. Metal-heavy production is considered one of the most leading and robust industries in world friendship. As a country that has achieved its economic independence in the world, Uzbekistan is also successfully mastering this direction of heavy industry at the expense of its domestic capabilities and potential. The company is considered one of the largest industrial sectors not only throughout the country, but also throughout the country. In the railway system, 90% of the need for goods is provided in the sex of these enterprises. During one second, the well-being of the "Hot Mechanical Plant" shoe company is working to melt metal several times and pour it into the necessary shapes. The company is currently working on the basis of high-tech technologies produced by KUNKELWAGNER in Germany. Today, the company is successfully working to extend their service life for various years while producing over-the-counter open and closed wagons and platforms. At the same time, import-substituting sinking, precautions and details

are being prepared there to repair the composition of the movement and railways.

Throughout the Republic of Uzbekistan, 7.4 million passengers were transported by commonly used highway. Passenger traffic increased by 751, 4 thousand compared to the corresponding period. On average, 27,4 thousand passengers used rail transport in one day. This figure is a sign of an increase of 2,8,000 compared to last year.

Thus, thanks to the great work done in this area, the importance of railways in the integration of our country with the world community has increased day by day.

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